

Proceedings
of the
26th Annual
Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference
in Adult, Continuing, Community,
and Extension Education

Proceedings Edited by
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Indiana University

Conference Held at
Ball State University – Alumni Center
September 25-27, 2007

Conference Hosted by
Ball State University
Muncie, Indiana

**26th Annual Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in
Adult, Continuing, Community, and Extension Education**

**September 25-27, 2007
Ball State University, Muncie, Indiana**

Dear Conference Participants:

This year Ball State University, Teachers College, and the Department of Educational Studies has enthusiastically accepted the responsibility of hosting the **26th Annual Midwest Research to Practice Conference for Adult, Continuing, Community, and Extension Education**. We welcome you as participants and presenters at this year's conference. The theme this year is "*Building Communities with Sustainability and Social Capital*." We are honored to have faculty, graduate students, and practitioners from the Midwest and beyond here with us

The conference prides itself on providing a supportive and developing forum for emerging to seasoned researchers to interact with one another and present and develop their research agendas.

We encourage graduate students to submit presentations alongside their mentors or faculty members and are happy to have a community where rank and title does not drive the content being presented. The conference provides access a forum for critical dialogue, feedback, and assistance in the development of a research agenda; and to formally and informally network and learn from the premier adult education researchers and practitioners throughout the Midwest region. I thank our BSU graduate students and others who have actively participated in the planning of activities for the Pre-Conference, including student poster presentations on sustainability and social capital.

We appreciate your participation and your insights into the important topics being shared over these three days. Welcome and make the most of this conference and networking experience. If you wish, you can find the conference papers the website at <http://mdudka.iweb.bsu.edu/mr2p2007>. They will be archived after the conference at IUPUI in the University Library Digital Collections at <http://www.ulib.iupui.edu/collections/digital/>.

Sincerely,

Michelle Dudka

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Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education

Mission Statement

This conference provides a forum for practitioners and researchers to discuss practices, concepts, evaluation, and research studies in order to improve practice in Adult Education. It facilitates dialogue and the initiation and pursuit of projects among individuals and groups working in various fields of Adult Education. Through such discussion and collaboration, participants contribute toward the realization of a more humane and just society through lifelong learning

Prepared on behalf of the Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference Steering Committee by
Boyd Rossing, May 28, 1991.

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Social Change and National Literacy Campaigns An Example from the Developing World: Turkish Village Institutes

Özlem Zabitgil

Abstract

Literacy has been a lifelong interest to (adult) educators nationally and internationally. 20th century in particular experienced various national and international literacy campaigns. Some of these regional or nationwide literacy campaigns aimed to impact social change and justice in addition to spreading literacy skills. It is not novel that many countries implemented literacy campaigns throughout history. France, Japan, Russia, Tanzania and Turkey are only a few of these. Educational activities, especially literacy movements are never free of politics or power dynamics. Literacy education is a political enterprise with imbedded values and interests, and thus calls for critical analysis. Village Institutes is an example of literacy reform from the developing world in 1930's Turkey. This literacy campaign is unique because of its context of continuing national transformation and the extent to which Turkey was able to change itself. The evaluation of such a national educational campaign holds significant insights for today's educational, literacy and social change goals with the changing needs of the contemporary age. This project illuminates the potential of educational/literacy reforms for impacting social change and justice as well as the precautions that need to be taken into account in their praxis.

Introduction

This research is a working progress towards my dissertation proposal. This preliminary report looks at TVI (Turkish Village Institutes) as a literacy reform for highlighting its multi goals, power and value system surround the TVI through the analysis of social, political and educational contexts. Adult Education/literacy as a discipline is based on the bricks of social change. Some adult educators are concerned about losing the original character of education and giving way to bureaucratic hierarchy. Discussions about the key goals of contemporary adult and literacy education continue. One of the key questions brought up by educators is, is adult education challenging or confirming the status quo? Also, Does (adult) education aim for individual, personal autonomy, or social, collective autonomy? Origins of adult education stem from social change goals. Social justice mission is visible through the praxis of Paulo Freire in Latin America and Myles Horton in Highlander Folk School. Finger (1995) argues that the original mission of Adult education might be unfavorable or counterproductive today. Similarly Heaney (1993) pinpoints that Adult Education today is marked with technical and skills teaching, technological training, homogenizing adults to the emerging needs of the contemporary system. Some of the diverse goals put forward by educators are to provide a second chance of education, bring job opportunities, career change, impart skills training, homogenize adults into the mainstream society, self fulfillment or to bring critical self awareness and possibility of social change to name a few of these goals.

Hass (1992) argues that Adult education has increasingly become a commodity to sell. He encourages embracing this commodity orientation towards adult education because we are living in an era of consumer society and market system. Yet, the dilemma of this learning market is crystal clear because the free choice is not free and not by choice either. In other words, educational system creates and reproduces inequalities (Edwards, 1995) by increasing the gap

between 'haves' and 'have nots' (Cunningham, 1993). Not everyone has access to education or the same educational opportunities. Considering the changing dialogue around the adult education/literacy, it becomes necessary to re-investigate, re-state and re-claim the contemporary goals of adult and literacy education.

Social justice goals of education needs to be reclaimed because adult education needs to commit to awakening learners critically to their positions in the world and alert them about the social structures they live in. Regardless of the changing demands of the educational enterprise, there is an undeniable due for the commitment of social change for including previously excluded groups if Adult Education/Literacy is to be true to its origins. Educational discrepancies should be acknowledged and educators need to create space for educational opportunities stretching beyond the learning market boundaries. In light of this emerging dialogue, it becomes all the more important to look at the past and diverse contexts with educational and literacy reforms as we determine today's educational priorities. With these barometers this paper looks at the Turkish Village Institutes as a national educational reform of Turkey in 1930s. This cultural context and era provides a platform of discussion about the particulars of Turkish educational context and the changing needs of today with the emerging goals of literacy education.

Literature Review

Think of a country that has lost massive land, and is left with little national pride and strength to survive: This is Turkey after WWI! Struggle against foreign powers to save empire's independence is paramount. Not to be colonized by foreign powers and to protect the remaining land for an independent nation created the Independence war with the leadership of Mustafa Kemal Ataturk (the father of Turks). This brought back the remnants of the lost hope and pride to reenergize the nation. This was the time when Ataturk proclaimed the Turkish Republic divorcing from the thousand year Ottoman theocracy. On one hand the (national) identity of the empire was shaken, on the other hand the uncertainty of newly born Republic intensified by multiple changes and reforms in the political, social, legal, economic, and cultural spheres such as alphabet reform, clothing reform, secularism etc. to name a few under the leadership of Ataturk (Mustafa Kemal). Brickman (1985) states that "Culturally and educationally, Turkey is Western, such as the North Atlantic Treaty Organization, the Council of Europe, and the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. The image of Turkey began to change in the outside world, as it opted and co-opted for new governing, lifestyle and identity following the 1920's. The question is, how smooth this transition has been, and what has been lost and gained along the way? Is it possible to change who one is at a split second? Is it conceivable to embrace the unknown by disrupting the known as in the case of Turkey?"

The proclamation of the Turkish Republic is a significant turning point in Turkish history, 1923. Turkey metamorphosed itself into a different life style, national and social character. This meant that the new republic decreed to conform to the principles of progressivism, modernization and westernization (Brickman, 1985). With the birth of the Turkish Republic the illiterate rural population formed an overwhelming portion of Turkey's total population. Also, the Educational act of a modernized educational system was set as law. "As President for 15 years, until his death in 1938, Mustafa Kemal Atatürk introduced a broad range of swift and sweeping reforms - in the political, social, legal, economic, and cultural spheres - virtually unparalleled in any other country" (<http://www.ataturk.org/index2.html>). Deep rooted changes were executed believing that this would allow for the following and sharing of western developments. Secularism was presented by abolishing the religious rule. From then on

religion dictated to be a private activity for individuals losing its once held power on the legal system. Some of large scale changes were: the disestablishment of Islam as the official religion of the country, the closing of religious schools, the ending of religious rule and the ending of the monarchy. (<http://www.ataturk.org/index2.html>).

As Turkey negotiates its new identity in a new system in the coming decade, Ismail Hakki Tonguc, one of the leading educators of the time, embarks upon a national literacy reform to educate the Turkish population. Turkish village institutes (TVI) is the progeny of the continuing national transformation and modernization in the early 20th century Turkey. The Turkish Village Institutes aims to educate all, -young and old- especially rural populations by reaching out the invisible corners of the rural Turkey. The village institutes in Turkey came into existence under economic constraints following general depression of the WWII. What makes Turkey's literacy reform unique is the extent to which Turkey stretched itself into a new identity by departing or denying a past heritage for a new existence. Turkey did not only aim to teach how to read and write and spread written literacy skills, but to transform the thousand year theocracy and erase its deep mark in the lives of people. And education is used as the main vehicle of imparting this changing national identity to the Turkish population.

The first and foremost goal of the TVI was to tackle the overwhelming illiteracy rate which was 89 % nationally and 94 % in the rural population (Karaomerlioglu, 2000). Similarly, the inequality in the allocation of economic resources, disparate educational opportunities and literacy services were paramount. Education is used as a vehicle for educational development as well as social change, modernization, secularization, and economic improvement. Education is aimed to mobilize the nation into becoming a more developed and hopefully more just populace through the function of the TVI. The Turkish Village Institutes (TVI) as a literacy reform is part and parcel of a larger project of modernization that preceded and succeeded the TVI.

The TVI represents multi-layered goals. The TVI is an educational reform first and foremost, but also a national reform of modernization and metamorphosis. One of the main goals of the TVI was described as the spreading of education to the masses. The appeal of the time was that it was necessary to break the bondage of illiteracy if Turkey was to be part of the Western developments. Through the dissemination of education especially to the previously ignored segments of the country, 5 central grand missions emerged: Modernization, Industrialization, Nation Building, Secularization, and Democratization. There were continuing debates as to the role of education and the goals of the TVI (Turkish Village Institutes) in spreading these new policies and new political stances. Education was seen as a powerful tool to be used to spread new ideologies. Education was utilized as a mechanism to break away from past traditions and embrace new ones.

During the 1930's period peasants and villagers had become a growing interest to the Republican elites (Karaomerlioglu, 2002). Before this period urban centers paid very little attention to villagers or their problems. Intelligentsia realized it was necessary to alleviate poverty, illiteracy, and lack of technological resources, which were commonplace among the rural population in order to develop as a nation. The numerical statistics indicate that: 30,000 villages out of the 35,000 villages had no school in the early 1930s (Arayici, 1999, p. 268). Turkish Village Institutes was created as a major instrument to educate the rural masses under the leadership of Ismail Hakki Tonguc as an educational experimentation. The name of Institutes was borrowed from French, and since they were built at the country side they are called Turkish Village Institutes. There have been various interpretations and claims as to the goals of the TVI as a literacy reform. It is necessary to highlight the basic premises of the TVI as the following: 1)

Train peasant youth as teachers 2) Free, post-primary, and co-education (Compulsory) 3) Economic development: 4) bring technology, modern production skills, and agricultural techniques

a) TVI as a work school: cooperative work b) Cultivate crops, construct institute buildings, raise animals c) 50 % of the curriculum is reserved for Culture Studies: Turkish, history, geography, citizenship, mathematics, chemistry, foreign language, physics, drawing, physical education, folk dances, music, home economics, and child care, pedagogy, cooperatives, and agriculture economics. d) 25 % curriculum devoted to Agriculture classes: Field crops, horticulture, industrial crops breeding, animal science, poultry production, honey bee production, aquaculture, and fishing. e) 25 % curriculum devoted to Technical classes: Blacksmithing, carpentry, building construction, and handicrafts 5) Food production, cooking, cleaning and planting etc. are self supplied by and for the school. 6) Weekly meetings for reflection, dialogue, and crisis/problem management, criticism, decision making. 7) Encouraging cultural production and exhibition of the rural identity. 8) Villagers had to work (~ 60 days annually) for the construction and repair of the institutes (along with teachers and students) 9) every village institute had around 100-300 hectares of land at their disposal. 10) 20 year compulsory service as a village teacher in their village upon graduation 11) those who did not accept this proposition, had to pay all the TVI education expenses to the government with interest rates. (Aktas, 1985 & Arayici, 1999 & Karaomerlioglu, 2002)

Theoretical and Methodological Frameworks

Critical approach to literacy is utilized for studying the Turkish Village Institutes. Because of its emphasis on political nature of literacy undertaking, Critical Approach to literacy is a viable framework for this study. Critical approach acknowledges that power and knowledge are invariably connected. This approach analyzes social system and one's standing in the system by linking the individual to the society. Similarly this approach studies history as a man made construction to be deconstructed and reconstructed in critical synthesis. Borrowing from Paulo Freire's praxis this approach connects 'reading the word' and 'reading the world'. Thus, literacy education/learning should move beyond the discrete skill instruction alone.

Critical approach to literacy does not only aim to literal teaching of literacy skills such as acquisition of phonemes, spelling skills, and deciphering of print literacy, but more importantly to engagement of critical thinking. Deweyan concept of 'growth' and exercise of 'critical intelligence' is applicable for the central tenets of the Critical literacy approach. Demetrian (2003) argues that "...to live, the student must learn conduct successful transactions with his/her environment...to grow the, the student must create novel forms of recognition and response" (1). With this in mind, critical literacy approach acknowledges the importance of the culture, identity and context in a learning experience and encourages an inquisitive mind towards the social structures and everyday ways of inequalities. Dialogue and critical consciousness are initial steps to lead the way for group consciousness and collective action. This framework encourages the study of TVI in relation to power, values and interests as represented in the texts.

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is employed as a methodology for this research undertaking, because of the political nature of literacy and literacy research accommodates the epistemological stance of the CDA. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) gains popularity especially after 1980s through the works of critical researchers like Fairclough, Wodak and Van Dijk's to name a few. Yet the discourse as a concept introduced widely by Foucault in 1960s refers to the shared knowledge and historical making of the language use. The idea of discourse

and discourse communities are prime importance. The shared rules system for a discourse functions as a gate keeper and thus permits or refuses entrance to different groups. Since there is not a literally marked discourse entrance in the society, the participation of a discourse is of a symbolic one. For example, those who are in the academic field have a discourse system which is intelligible and accessible only to those who are familiar of that specific discourse. There are multiple discourses and different rules and membership norms exist. Locke (2004) explains discourse as giving meaning to the world via 'sense making stories' (5). Similarly for Gee (1996) discourse is 'forms of life' and "ways of being in the world" (viii). Others define discourse as any social transaction such as a text, speech, face to face conversational exchange, an online communication, news or any media content etc. which embody cultural, social, and power relationships (Luke, 2004). Du Gay's (1996, p.43) definition of discourse emphasizes the central role of the language. Thus discourse for him is "... a group of statements which provide a language for talking about a topic and a way of producing a particular kind of knowledge about a topic. Thus the term refers both to the "production of knowledge through language and representations and the way that knowledge is institutionalized, shaping social practices and setting new practices into play" (Ainsworth & Hardy, 2004:236). These few definitions vary in degrees but nevertheless they emphasize discourse as a sense making mechanism, which includes membership (inclusion and exclusion) in its operation.

One of the leading names in the CD (Critical Discourse) analysis, Norman Fairclough, defines CDA's aim as "to systematically explore often opaque relationships of causality and determination between a) discursive practices, events, and texts, and b) wider social and cultural structures, relations and processes; to investigate how such practices, events and texts arise out of and are ideologically shaped by relations of power and struggles over power" (Fairclough, 1995: 132). With this very statement the CDA translates as a methodology which pursues justice, and equity in its practice. The CDA is political methodology. Hence, it has a firm purpose of exposing unjust power structures and how they operate in social relations. CDA pays particular attention to the relationship of language, power, and identity as can be discerned from the key words as discourse membership, inclusion and exclusion. The study of language is at the centre of CDA, yet at the same time language forms only one of the various discourses that were mentioned above. In this methodology language is not seen as a neutral vehicle of communication, but a system of discourses, which in its use includes, excludes, privileges and oppresses. Gee (1999) reminds the loaded nature of language use: "Language has a magical property; when we speak or write we craft what we have to say to fit the situation or context" (1999: 11). The importance of language for the CDA is its utilization of language as a means of discourse transaction and normalization of these political acts. Locke (2004) perceives this to be shaped and reshaped by various forms of ideological discourses. Language use is an active process of construction. Fairclough (1995) emphasizes the 'construction', 'constructing' and 'construct'. Language constructs discourses, and yet at the same time is constructed through discourses. There is an ongoing two way relation between language and discourses, which emphasize possibility of reinforcing a particular discourse or creating a suspense or tension by refusing the transaction. Additionally, it highlight the continuing and unfinishedness of any discourse, which gives hope for change, which is captured by Rogers (2003) as language's function as "socially constitutive, that is constructing and constructed by social life" (Rogers, 2003:7). It is in this construction that we make, remake and reshape our realities and worlds.

Conclusion

Just as language is not a neutral vehicle of communication neither is education an impartial ground for teaching or learning. Education is a human enterprise, and is very much like other human activities is a political ground for conflicts of power, agency and values (Kincheloe, 2004). The goals of education and literacy programs change with the emerging needs, goals and interests of its time. The synthesis of a national educational campaign as Turkish Village Institutes holds significant insights for today's educational, literacy and social change goals. Not only we learn about the aspirations, accomplishments, dilemmas and shortcomings of Turkish educational context and politics, but also gain significant practical and theoretical implications for today's educational and literacy goals. As the face of the Adult Education and Adult Literacy changes in the contemporary age, this research inquiry of working progress holds crucial implications to learn from.

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